

POST-COVID POWER SHIFTS: US-CHINA RIVALRY AND INDIA'S EMERGING ROLE

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Abstract

As the 21st century has been deemed as Asian century, questions arise about the potential decline of US hegemony and the rise of China as a formidable global player. The relative decline of US hegemony has been advantageous for China, leading to a competitive dynamic between the two countries in various domains. Moreover, the way the US had responded to the Covid-19 crisis may have further accelerated its relative decline. As the world is becoming increasingly multipolar, emerging countries like India are poised to play significant roles. This paper examines the transformative impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the global world order, particularly focusing on US-China rivalry and India's emerging role. Having emerged in Wuhan, China, Covid-19 rapidly escalated into a Public Health Emergency of International Concern, forcing nations worldwide into lockdowns to mitigate virus transmission. This crisis not only posed wide socio-political and economic challenges but also challenged the existing paradigm of "Complex Interdependence" among nations, leading to a re-evaluation of international relationships and alliances. This paper is a qualitative study of US-China rivalry post the pandemic through the lens of Covid-19, analysing its implications for the post-pandemic world order and the prospects it holds for emerging nations like India. This research paper draws data from both primary and secondary sources in order to provide the holistic picture of post Covid US- China rivalry.

Keywords: *China, complex interdependence, Covid-19, hegemony, Post-Cold War Order, US, World Order.*

Introduction

As Arundhati Roy rightly point outs in *The Pandemic Is a Portal*, historically pandemics have compelled humanity to reassess its past and reimagine its future. (Roy, 2020) Similarly, the COVID-19 crisis, too, has

acted as a gateway which marked a significant rupture with the pre-pandemic world and forged way to enter into a new era defined by dynamic global power shifts, altered geopolitical priorities, and changing international relationships. The COVID-19 pandemic which has become a familiar term for the past few years had sent shockwaves through both political and economic systems across the globe (Miller, 2020). It brought daily life to a halt whereby, nations went into lockdown, schools and workplaces were closed, and movement and trade were heavily restricted due to the fear of transmission of the virus. Police forces were also deployed to enforce these curbs, and civil liberties were curtailed in ways that raised alarm about democratic backsliding. This unprecedented global disruption revealed vulnerabilities in governance, healthcare systems, and institutional trust, marking a rupture with what was previously considered 'normal.'

Economically, the pandemic had hit hard, especially in service sector economy which is heavily dependent on human intervention such as travel, hospitality, aviation, real estate, textiles, and automobiles (Miller, 2020). But the impact of the crisis extended beyond public health and economics. It deepened an already strained international order, compelling governments to respond not only to immediate emergencies but also to rising political polarization, declining institutional legitimacy, and heightened global rivalries (Crawford, 2020). Therefore, COVID-19 did not create a disorder from scratch, rather it only amplified the pre-existing issues, which became more visible during the time of the crisis (News, 2020) As Rory Medcalf rightly notes, the pandemic has made long-standing flaws in the international system more visible (Crawford, 2020)

One of the most visible fault lines sharpened by the pandemic was the rivalry between the United States and China. As both countries have been trying to assert their power in the global world, to control the narrative and expand their influence, it led to the emergence of competition of global leadership during the pandemic. Both countries entered into a game of blaming and shaming each other, for instance, the US criticized China for its alleged lack of transparency in the early stages of the outbreak, while China, in turn, launched aggressive diplomatic efforts to recast its image as a responsible global power through vaccine diplomacy, aid shipments, and narratives about the effectiveness of its governance model. This mutual distrust between both the countries fuelled a broader

geopolitical and ideological competition between liberal democracies and authoritarian regimes. The pandemic thus acted as a catalyst, accelerating the strategic rivalry between the two powers and reshaping alliances, trade relationships, and the global perception of leadership and legitimacy.

At the same time, crisis also exposed serious flaws in global institutions like the WHO and the UN, whose delayed and inadequate responses led to the erosion of public trust and raised doubts about their credibility. Scholars like Sara Davies (Davies, 2008) have long critiqued the WHO for being influenced by powerful countries and the COVID-19 crisis seems to validate those concerns. Rather than acting swiftly and impartially, the WHO appeared hesitant, and critics argue it aligned too closely with China's narrative during the early stages of the outbreak (Pant H. V., 2020) This perception of institutional bias and inaction led many to question the reliability and neutrality of global health governance structures while also escalating tensions between the US and China. Hal Brands in one of his interviews for book "COVID and World Order: The Future of Conflict, Competition and Cooperation" says, "The Coronavirus crisis was a shock, but should not have been a surprise." (Frank Gavin, 2020) He argues that there have been numerous warning indicators, like H1N1, SARS, and MERS, that specialists have used to warn of such a pandemic for years. Nevertheless, we weren't ready for it. He also makes the point that we disregarded the two sets of warnings for this pandemic, the first of which was the WHO's early warning system, which for a number of complex reasons did not sound an alarm as it did in mid-January, and the second of which was related to the US's subpar leadership at both the domestic and global levels. (Frank Gavin, 2020)

As this paper primarily focuses on the evolving dynamics between the United States and China, it's important to recall realist scholar John Mearsheimer's argument that China has been maximising its power not for its security but for its supremacy. This is evident in its expansive global strategies from the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) to the String of Pearls strategy and more recently, its Health Silk Road, launched during the COVID-19 pandemic, (on similar lines of the BRI model)to create influence through vaccine diplomacy (Huang, 2014)). These efforts signal China's intention to leverage global crises as strategic openings to enhance its international clout.

In contrast, the United States which was once seen as the uncontested global power, adopted more inward looking approach during the initial phase of the pandemic, focusing on vaccine nationalism through advance purchase agreements and export restrictions (Usher, 2021) Its withdrawal from multilateral platforms, including WHO and COVAX, created a power vacuum that China used strategically to its advantage (Lee S. , 2021) However, under President Biden, the US rejoined WHO and COVAX, signalling a return to global engagement as an attempt to restore America's global image through renewed cooperation with institutions like the WHO. (Boasiako, 2022) The USA's response to the 2020 pandemic has been compared to the Obama administration's quick response to the 2014 Ebola outbreak in West Africa. In that case, a strong unilateral response was joined with a strong international response, which was lacking in the case of the Covid 19 pandemic. This time, the US administration failed to recognise the severity of the situation and instead chose to take unilateral actions that seemed more discouraging in light of the pandemic's underlying global nature. Such a response by the US government has eroded trust in its capability and competency as a global leader.

Therefore, this shift in the power dynamics highlighted an underlying strategic competition between the two nations, each attempting to shape the post-pandemic world order in its favor. Yet, alongside these challenges, COVID-19 has also created space for emerging or middle powers, such as India to position themselves as the frontrunners in the fight against the coronavirus. A country like India in contrast, has exhibited kindness, unity, goodwill, collective security, and humanitarian cooperation by disseminating the medicine hydroxylchloroquine (HCQ) to the world for humanitarian reasons. India has also demonstrated to the rest of the world the importance of ethics, knowledge, and leadership in times of crises. (Chaturvedi, 2020) In many ways, this crisis served as a reminder that every disruption also presents an opportunity resonating with the saying by Winston Churchill, “Never let a crisis go to waste”.

Beyond geopolitics, the pandemic has had a significant social impact. It compelled people to re-evaluate what really matters like strengthening family ties, improving hygiene practices, and fostering a deeper sense of gratitude and collective responsibility. Covid 19 has brought people into a war, it is not a conventional war but a war where whole world is involved in and high level of cooperation is important to fight against this virus.

(Chaturvedi, 2020) At the same time, it intensified existing rivalries, particularly between the US and China, as each tried to use the pandemic to reaffirm its global leadership.

COVID-19 as a Turning Point in Global Order

The COVID-19 pandemic can be seen as an “*epochal moment*” (Nicholas Ross Smith, 2020) in international relations, one that has shaken the foundations of the existing world order. History has been a testament that times of conflict, catastrophe, and unrest can result in changes to existing international arrangements. (Nicholas Ross Smith, 2020) Traditionally, given the dynamic nature of the world order, it has been shaped by how global powers responded to crises and managed their influence. Since World War II, the United States and its democratic allies have largely led this system. (Ross, 2020) However, the pandemic has exposed to the growing tendencies toward nationalism and isolation, while raising questions about the future of globalization as pandemic is not only a global health emergency, but it also highlights the fragility of globalization and weak spots in global governance. At the same time, it has made it clear that no country can combat global crises like pandemics in isolation therefore, international cooperation remains indispensable.

As Branko Milanovic from the London School of Economics pointed out that the post-pandemic world will likely be defined by a sense of uncertainty and loss of individual autonomy where even everyday decisions like where to go or how to spend time will be difficult. (Suljagic, 2020) Therefore, this sense of disorder has only intensified the existing rivalry between the United States and China, thereby resulting into changes in the existing world order.

World Order: Reimagined in the Wake of COVID-19

This section explores the concept of world order which has seen transformation in the wake of Covid-19. As a simplified definition the arrangement of power and authority that serves as the foundation for conducting international relations and world politics is referred to as the “world order”. It is a dynamic concept which keeps on changing on the basis of many external factors. From the 1648 Treaty of Westphalia to the end of the Cold War, we’ve seen the global order reshape itself repeatedly and in the 21st century, a key development has been the rise of emerging economies. 21st century is multipolar with cooperative face which is built

on material interests resulting from deepening systemic interdependence among states. This multipolarity is driven by deep economic interdependence and strategic cooperation as the centre of gravity of International economy has shifted towards Asia Pacific. While the United States still continues to wield immense influence, its relative dominance is declining which some scholars like Thomas Wright have extensively debated. (Thomas Wright, 2021) Even, Henry Kissinger, one of the key architects of the post-Cold War order, argued that "*the coronavirus pandemic will forever alter the world order.*" (Kissinger, 2020)

In fact, Goldman Sachs predicted that by 2030, the collective GDP of BRIC nations would surpass that of the G7. Similarly, echoing this shift, Fareed Zakaria famously called it the dawn of a "*post-American world,*" one that is marked by 'decline of west and rise of the rest'. (Zakaria, 2008). However, there are some scholars who suggest that rather than a collective rise of BRICS or BASIC nations, what we are really witnessing is the singular rise of China. The complex economic interdependence between China and the US what Niall Ferguson termed "*Chimerica*" (Browne, 2022) has grown increasingly strained. Former Secretary of State Henry Kissinger compared today's standoff between US and China to the 'foothills' of a new Cold War. (Crawford, 2020) According to Rory Medcalf, author of *Indo-Pacific Empire*, the key challenge now isn't just how the U.S. responds to China's rise, but whether "middle players" including India, Australia, Japan and Europe are prepared to take risks to defend the international order and to work together in doing so. (Crawford, 2020)

Despite China's growing assertiveness, it has also triggered friction with several other countries which to some extent marred China's global image. For instance, tensions with Australia over the origins of the virus, with Canada over the detention of Huawei Technologies Co. Executive meng Wanzhou, with India over a disputed border, with US over trade war and even with south East Asian nations for the islands in the South China Sea. Even Hong Kong protested over China's national security law which has spurred global anger against China's interference in the former British territory's interdependence, severing relations with Britain. (Chaturvedi, 2020). In fact, according to Agatha Kratz, a Paris-based associate director at Rhodium Group who leads research on EU-China relation, Europe's attitude to China is hardening inexorably, helped by a rapid shift in public opinion against Beijing. Similarly, according to

William Choong, senior fellow at the ISEAS Yusof Ishak Institute in Singapore tensions are also high with Taiwan and in the disputed South China Sea and the East China Sea amid a “*hyper-power display*” by China. Given the fact that Covid-19 had emerged in China there has been a lot of erosion of China’s political, social and economic standing. China has also been accused of delivering countries that were purchasing PPE kits from China suboptimal and used PPE kits, inefficient chemicals, and components for sanitizers. (Chaturvedi, 2020) Nevertheless, despite such an outrage against China, it used pandemic aid to project soft power as an attempt to repair its reputation.

Ian Bremmer, president of the Eurasia Group, mentions three major post-pandemic trends that are going to shape the future of global order: First, deglobalisation which is reflected through logistical challenges in terms of global supply chains which have been witnessed during this crisis; second, the rise of nationalism and “*my nation first*” politics, which will compel businesses to localise their operations that support national and supply chains as economic troubles worsens; and third, China’s geopolitical rise which has been happening since three decades might be affected (Bremmer, 2020) Hars V Pant also argues that post COVID-19 , there will be a new kind of Cold War but this time centered on China and the United States. The rivalry now influences everything from global health policies to digital infrastructure, trade norms, and climate action. (Pant H. V., 2021)

Intensification of US-China Rivalry in the Wake of COVID-19

The United States and China have been embroiled in a geopolitical conflict since the beginning of the 21st century. In the recent years following the pandemic, the U.S.-China rivalry has escalated across multiple domains:

Trade and Economic Tensions: Trade related tensions is one of the key concerns between US-China. Today, China is the third largest export market for the US, behind Canada and Mexico, with US exports to China exceeding \$195 billion in 2024. While US remains China’s top export destination. The U.S. trade deficit with China in 2024 stood at \$295 billion, still the largest with any single country, though the lowest since 2009. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) Economic tensions goes back to 2018 when President Trump launched a trade war, imposing tariffs on hundreds of billions of dollars’ worth of Chinese goods, reaching as high as 145%

by his second term (April 2025). Then China in response imposed retaliatory tariffs going up to 125% on U.S. products. Even President Biden largely retained Trump's tariffs, \$360 billion worth and raised them further in strategic sectors. For instance, tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles were quadrupled, tripled on steel and aluminium, and doubled on semiconductors. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) Trump's 32% tariff on Taiwanese goods (with semiconductors exempted) and his executive order to restructure CHIPS Act implementation show a tougher stance. China challenged the U.S. at the WTO in February 2025, accusing it of violating trade rules, but trust in the WTO system is eroding on both sides. Despite tariffs, China's state subsidies, labour abuses, and overcapacity continue to distort global markets, leading many in the U.S. to call for tighter restrictions and reduced dependency. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) Despite these strains, experts agree that full economic decoupling is unlikely due to deep interdependence. China still holds around \$760 billion in U.S. Treasury bonds, making it the second-largest foreign holder after Japan, further highlighting the deep financial interdependence. With the two nations accounting for 43% of global GDP and nearly 48% of global manufacturing in 2023, any disruption in their economic ties sends shockwaves throughout the global economy. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) These actions have disrupted global trade and supply chains, with both economies facing significant challenges. Notably, China has introduced export controls on rare earth minerals, critical for various industries, further complicating the economic landscape. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) However, despite these measures, experts argue that the tariffs haven't solved the underlying issues. Studies show that U.S. companies and consumers bear much of the cost, and Chinese manufacturing often finds alternate routes through third countries like Vietnam or Mexico, weakening the intended effect of the trade restrictions. Nevertheless, tariffs remain in place, and export controls and tech rivalry continue to escalate.

Technological Competition: When it comes technological supremacy, both countries have been at forefront. Especially in artificial intelligence and semiconductor development which has become a focal point of their rivalry. As China floods global markets with cheap electric vehicles and solar products, The U.S. has implemented restrictions on chip sales to China, aiming to curb its technological advancements. In fact TikTok's forced sale in 2024 and export bans on advanced chips also reflect fears

over data privacy and tech espionage. New export controls now block China's access to advanced U.S. technologies, and some U.S. investments in Chinese tech sectors have been restricted due to national security concerns. The Biden administration further banned U.S. investment in critical Chinese technologies and restricted bulk data transfers. These efforts have hurt China's access to cutting-edge semiconductors, yet also sparked domestic innovation for instance, in January 2025, Chinese startup DeepSeek launched a next-gen AI model, reportedly cheaper and more energy-efficient than U.S. counterparts like OpenAI's GPT or Google DeepMind. (CFR.orgEditors, 2025) Despite these efforts, Chinese companies like Huawei are rapidly closing the gap, with experts noting that China is "very, very close" to the U.S. in the AI chip race. (Business Insider, 2025)

Military and Geopolitical Strains: Tensions have also escalated in the geopolitical arena, with increased military activities around Taiwan and the South China Sea. (Reuters, 2025) The U.S. has bolstered its support for Taiwan, while China has conducted large-scale military drills in the region. These developments have raised concerns about potential conflicts and the stability of the Indo-Pacific region.

Global Influence and Diplomacy: Both nations are in race to have stronger global influence, with China expanding its presence in regions like Latin America through infrastructure projects, such as the proposed observatory in Chile. (APNEWS, 2025) The U.S. views these moves with suspicion, fearing they may serve as avenues for intelligence gathering and geopolitical leverage. (APNEWS, 2025)

Although there have tensions between the US and China for a very long time, but the COVID-19 pandemic had significantly deepened their rivalry. Scholars had suggested of the two distinct political trends as a result of this crisis: first, a shift towards greater isolation and reduced connectivity; second, or a renewed push for international cooperation. While complete isolation proved to be counterproductive, whereas targeted distancing especially to curb virus transmission highlighted the importance of coordinated global responses. (Nicholas Ross Smith, 2020).Historically, major crises have often resulted into structural reforms, and similarly the pandemic has exposed the fragility of global institutions and highlighted the need for a reimagined, more resilient model of globalization. Democratic nations such as Taiwan, South Korea,

and New Zealand, alongside semi-authoritarian states like Singapore, responded more effectively to the pandemic than some expected global leaders like US, UK etc. In contrast, the United States faced a credibility crisis across dimensions of power, wealth, and legitimacy. Its inadequate pandemic leadership created a strategic vacuum, which gave China a space to project itself as a responsible global actor through extensive medical aid and diplomacy (Pant, 2020; Samant, 2020). This shift challenged the traditional liberal order and raised concerns about the declining influence of American leadership in global governance. In such a scenario, US' status as a global leader has been tested over three main elements which are power, wealth and legitimacy but during the Coronavirus pandemic US leadership seemed to fail the test and the void which was left by US leadership proved as an advantage to China. While both US and China engaged in a mutual blame game, it had a huge impact at international level. President Trump accused China of unleashing an attack “*worse than Pearl Harbor*” and “*worse than the World Trade Centre*” (Samant, 2020), whereas China, on the other hand, asserted that the virus was created by the American military (Samant, 2020)

As the virus was originated in Wuhan, it raised global suspicion towards China. Even it has been referred to as China's Chernobyl by some. (Herman, 2021) In response, Beijing launched a diplomatic campaign, offering medical supplies and aid, though much of it was criticized as substandard (Nicholas Ross Smith, 2020). However, China's effort to position itself as a global saviour was seen by many as a calculated move to fill the leadership vacuum created by US withdrawal from multilateralism. The Trump administration's decision to halt WHO funding and abstain from key G20 and WHO meetings reinforced this perception of American isolationism (Pant H. V., 2020) US also struggled to meet its own domestic needs, let alone assist allies. The lack of coordination even with Europe had deeply undermined its credibility. Various moves by US, for instance, Trump's abrupt travel bans and America First rhetoric further alienated traditional partners and exposed a fractured leadership (Samant, 2020) and the resulting vacuum allowed China to portray itself as indispensable, despite ongoing scepticism about its transparency and motives.

Moreover, the rivalry also reflected competing models of governance between the two countries. In a way China's authoritarian capitalism appeared more effective in crisis response than the polarized US

administration. Meanwhile, China's medical diplomacy, particularly in Italy, Iran, and Serbia, proved to be effective in expanding its soft power and global influence. However, this activity was also criticised by U.S. President Donald Trump under the heading "Chinese debt policy." (Kupeli, 2020)

COVID-19 has served as a stark reminder of the global dependency on a few centralized hubs, particularly China for manufacturing and the US for finance. Given the era of globalisation, today's global socioeconomic infrastructure works like a hub and spoke model in which all nodes are connected to the hub by short distances, central hubs performs the essential functions for example financial activity is concentrated in United States, while China is the world's manufacturing centre. Since the essential functions are concentrated in the hub, it can create a systemic risk, failure in the hub can lead to cascading effect, creating problems in the interconnected nodes just like the 2008 financial crisis that originated in the US. Similarly, during the pandemic disruption of medical supply chains made democracies reevaluate their overreliance on authoritarian regimes like China for critical goods such as PPE and APIs (Brands, 2020). Therefore, emerging countries can play a huge role for just like like India, Japan, and Australia in response to become less reliant on China launched the Supply Chain Resilience Initiative (SCRI). Countries like Germany and Australia had also tightened their laws to guard against Chinese acquisitions of strategic assets.

Scholars argued that COVID-19 marked a turning point in global power politics. According to Hal Brands, the pandemic crystallized a strategic competition already underway between the two powers. It reflected not only a struggle for military dominance in the Indo-Pacific but also for normative leadership over whether liberal democracy or authoritarian capitalism would shape the global order (Brands, 2020). It is believed by scholars that much of China's success will depend on what happens in US. Therefore, scholars have warned US of exceptional rise of China where it is believed that China is not maximising its power for security but maximising its power for increasing its dominance. Historian Hal Brands says that we are going to look back on COVID in the way that we now look back on the events with respect to the Cold War, as the event that really crystallized an emerging competition between two great powers and made everyone realize that it was going on. Similarly here there are various specific issues driving this competition between US and China.

China's regional ambitions, evident through the Belt and Road Initiative and assertiveness in the South China Sea, suggested a broader effort to reshape global governance in its favour. Subsequently challenging the US led International system by projecting its power through such actions. In response, scholars called for the US to bolster alliances, invest in critical technologies, and reduce economic dependence on China (Mearsheimer, 2019). The US must create a robust, more resilient, competitive, and free-market economy without necessarily exposing itself to undue influence or weakness because of its reliance on Chinese technology or the Chinese market. In order to assure that democracies take the lead in creating AI and other technologies that will drive the 21st century economy and military effectiveness, the US must invest in such technology. US should follow a multilateral collective policy as well. In light of the aforementioned situation, the US must strengthen the military balance of power in the Western Pacific. It can engage like-minded countries to counter China, initiatives like QUAD group can be seen as one. (Mearsheimer, 2019)

So, as was the case with the bounded orders ruled by Moscow and Washington during the Cold War, the rivalry between the China-led and U.S.-led bounded regimes would encompass both full-throated economic and military combat. The major difference this time is that, unlike during the Cold War, the international order will play a significant role in controlling the cooperative features of the global economy. (Mearsheimer, 2019) In this new world order the emerging countries like India will also have a crucial role to play.

India's Emerging Global Role in the Post-Covid Era: Opportunities and Strategic Imperatives

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented both challenges and unprecedented opportunities for emerging economies like India to redefine their roles in the international order. India's strategic response to the pandemic through its health diplomacy, technological innovation, and proactive multilateral engagement has strengthen its global image and highlighted avenues for deeper influence in the evolving global world order.

1. Shift in Global Supply Chains: India as an Alternative Hub

The pandemic exposed the world to the overdependence on China. As countries searched to diversify supply chains, India positioned itself as a key alternative manufacturing and pharmaceutical hub. Campaigns like 'Make in India', 'Production Linked Incentive (PLI)' schemes have been significant in making India as a viable alternative. (Bhutani, 2020) Even Multinational companies, including Apple, started relocating or expanding manufacturing operations in India, signalling a longer-term shift in production networks (Reuters, 2025)

2. Vaccine Diplomacy and Soft Power Expansion

India's vaccine diplomacy during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly through initiatives such as Vaccine Maitri (meaning "Vaccine Friendship") not only helped strengthen its political and strategic ties with neighbouring and global countries but also interacted with religious and moral value systems. (Boasiako, 2022). By mid-2021, India had exported over 66 million vaccine doses to nearly 100 countries, including low-income and middle-income nations (Mondal, 2024) India's Vaccine Maitri initiative further helped in strengthening India's image as "*pharmacy of the world*," a title earned through its generic pharmaceutical industry. (Kumar, 2021) India's efforts stood in contrast to the rising tide of "*vaccine nationalism*" among high-income countries. This not only addressed immediate global health needs but also enhanced India's soft power, positioning it as a benevolent and responsible international actor amid rising concerns about vaccine nationalism.

3. Leadership in Digital Public Infrastructure

Covid-19 also presented an opportunity to accelerate India's digital transformation. Platforms such as Aarogya Setu (contact tracing), CoWIN (vaccination management), and the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) became global benchmarks for scalable, low-cost digital public goods. These innovations highlighted India's capacity to design and implement digital solutions for large populations, and many developing nations began exploring similar frameworks inspired by India's model (WEF, 2023)

4. India as a Responsible Global Actor

In the early phase of the pandemic, when India was already in the middle of internal shortages, yet India exported hydroxychloroquine and paracetamol to over 100 countries, including the United States and Brazil (The Economic Times, 2020) India positioned itself as a responsible and benevolent power through its Vaccine Maitri initiative, under which it supplied millions of vaccine doses to neighbouring countries and other low- and middle-income nations across Asia, Africa, and the Caribbean. India also collaborated with global platforms like GAVI and COVAX, thereby promoting itself as the “*pharmacy of the world*” while enhancing regional goodwill and soft power (Marlow, 2021; Wintour, 2021). This initiative helped India reinforce its image as a humanitarian leader and a key player in global health governance.

5. Strategic and Multilateral Engagement

India leveraged the pandemic to deepen strategic partnerships and gain greater geopolitical visibility. Within multilateral forums such as the Quad, G20, BRICS, and COVAX, India actively advocated for equitable access to vaccines, health resources, and pandemic recovery mechanisms (White House, 2021). Prime Minister Narendra Modi also advocated for a greater proportion of India's representation at the UN in his speech during the UNGA's 75th session (Samant, 2020)

Vision for the Future: Realizing Post-Pandemic Potential

As the post-pandemic world was marked by uncertainty and realignment, Indian leadership has underlined the importance of readiness, resilience, and reform. Prime Minister Modi emphasized that “*This decade is a very important one, just like the decade after the Second World War. Unlike earlier, we are not going to be a mute spectator. We will rise to the occasion based on our traditions and ideals of Vasudheva Kutumbakam*” (PTI, 2021) and he implied that India will no longer be a passive observer but an active global participant guided by the values of Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam (PTI, 2021).

Similarly, N Chandrasekaran, Chairman of Tata Sons observes that there is a need for a strategic national focus on regulatory norms on data privacy, data residency, data localization, and taxation in general. (PTI, 2020) Along with this, focusing on digital bandwidth expansion, and cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence and robotics to

empower India's manufacturing and innovation ecosystem is also crucial. He also emphasized the rethinking of supply chains and self-reliance in renewable energy and food security as he states that coronavirus pandemic "*exacerbated global supply chains and clearly outlined a new global world order*", Chandrasekaran reiterated that "*2020 marks the decoupling of China and the US. What it means is countries and companies will need to de risk and balance their supply chain*" in the future (PTI, 2020) He also claims that due to the pandemic, India needs to concentrate on issues like solar manufacturing, energy efficiency in the transportation sector, and rethinking our food supply chain. (PTI, 2020) Even Dr. Mike Ryan , World Health Organization emergencies programme director ,echoed this potential, noting that the trajectory of the global COVID-19 response largely depended on India's capabilities and actions, given its track record in eradicating smallpox and polio.

Key Post-Pandemic Opportunities for India

Covid 19, no doubt has provided many possibilities for India. However, in order to take advantage of these opportunities, India must be well prepared. Bhutani (2020) highlights five pivotal areas where India can assert leadership in the post-COVID order:

1. **Healthcare Innovation:** India needs to expand its investments its public health infrastructure, pharmaceutical R&D, and assert leadership in affordable vaccine production. The Serum Institute of India and Bharat Biotech's development of indigenous vaccines during the Covid-19 have serve as strong precedents. India has been recognised as a leader in delivering vaccination to the countries who cannot afford it and where larger countries like the USA have failed to do so, particularly where there is a growing concern about vaccine nationalism
2. **Sanitation and Public hygiene:** given India's dense population and existence of slums often raise the red flags regarding sanitation and public hygiene in our country. Covid 19 has been like a wakeup call in order to alert everyone about importance of sanitation and public hygiene. India's nationwide sanitation program "Swacch Bharat Abhiyan " has been a milestone in achieving sanitation and public hygiene across the country . Nevertheless, it is important to ensure the effective implementation of such initiatives to have the real outcome.

3. **Inter-Governmental Coordination:** The internal migrant crisis during the lockdowns highlighted governance gaps. India witnessed exodus of migrants from their destination state to their source state , this has also given an opportunity for India in order to tackle the problem of migrants even at the global level . Therefore, This experience can catalyze better federal coordination and inform India's participation in global discussions on labor mobility and human rights.
4. **Reducing Animal Product Dependency:** With most pandemics (COVID-19, HIV, SARS, Nipah virus, Ebola, swine flu)being zoonotic in origin, India can lead in promoting plant-based dietary alternatives and sustainable agriculture to reduce reliance on animal products.
5. **Supply Chain Resilience and Technological Upgradation:** In the backdrop of evolving trends of de-globalisation and protectionism, India needs to make sure that it becomes a significant part of supply chains; it needs to make certain reforms with regard to its manufacturing sector and by employing state of the art technology in order to boost innovation and to establish itself as one of the leading countries in the global supply chain. India must reform its regulatory environment to attract investment, digitize its manufacturing sector, and integrate robotics and AI to become a hub of global supply chains.

Historically, global crises have led to new innovations and irrevocable change in the existing order whereby reshaping leadership dynamics. After the First World War, it was the leadership of Woodrow Wilson. It was Franklin D Roosevelt who played a leading role post Second World War. Today, as multilateral institutions like the UN and WHO are facing credibility issues, India's model of compassionate leadership, evidenced during the pandemic, offers an ethical counterpoint. New leadership is going to emerge in the post Covid world and India cannot afford not to be a part of it .India's support for SAARC, G20 cooperation, and e-diplomacy initiatives like virtual summits shows its commitment to multilateralism, even as geopolitical tensions rise. Covid 19 has created the circumstances where there is no loser or winner, as every country has lost something. China, in fact, has lost a lot of its social, economic and political standing. India has shown compassion, togetherness, bonhomie collective security, and humanitarian cooperation by sharing with the

world the drug hydroxylchloroquine (HCQ) on humanitarian grounds. With the end of Covid-19, we have witnessed realignment of the world order. India has shown the world the value of ethics, knowledge, sharing and above all the honesty and integrity in leading from the front in crisis situations. The New World Order will depend on e-diplomacy, Covid crisis has paved the way for virtual summits through video conferencing. Interdependence and greater political coordination will be the defining characteristics of the new world order.

Conclusion

Covid 19 has led to changes and can be considered as a turning point in the realm of International Relations. It is high time to bring out various reforms which are long overdue. Institutional reforms hold high significance given the role WHO and UN have played during this crisis. It is time to be critical of the role of these institutions where they have failed to do much to prevent this crisis. WHO has been accused of not revealing the information about the Covid 19 when it first came to its knowledge. Had WHO warned about it earlier, the crisis could have been prevented at such a wide scale. US which should have responded quickly but it really did not do so. How countries like US and China have responded to the crisis will determine the post Covid world order. The time where the problems have become transnational like climate change, terrorism, cyber threats and most importantly the current crisis of Covid, it is highly important to have a cooperative and multilateral approach along with strong leadership because only strong leadership can solve global problems related to travel restrictions, information sharing, and the flow of critical goods. Given these diversified nature of threats, countries should come together in order to contain such crisis. Countries like India have an opportunity to establish themselves as the leading countries where it will play an important role in the coming years. Since the gravity of International politics and economy has shifted to Indo-Pacific is a push factor for India to establish itself as a net security provider In Indian Ocean Region. Countries like US and China should come together rather than getting into war of narratives. It is to be remembered that this crisis has affected almost all the countries across world and coming together with a multilateral approach things can be resolved amicably.

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